

A Cross Sectional Study to Assess Activities of Daily Living of Elderly in an Urban Area of Western MaharashtraAditi Yadav¹, Rajesh Shetty², Ravi Nimonkar³, PMP Singh⁴¹Resident, Dept. of Community Medicine, Armed Forces Medical Services,²Assistant Professor, Dept. of Community Medicine, Armed Forces Medical Services^{3,4}Professor, Dept. of Community Medicine, Armed Forces Medical Services

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Population ageing is an inevitable and irreversible demographic reality. With longevity and declining fertility rates, the population of persons 60 years and above is globally growing faster than the general population. The proportion of the elderly in India has been increasing swiftly in recent years. The trend is likely to continue in the coming decades. The share of population over the age of 60 years is projected to increase from 10.5 percent in 2022 to 20.8 percent in 2050. By the end of the century, the elderly will constitute over 36 percent of the total population of India. Health professionals refer to the ability or the inability to perform the Activities of daily living (ADLs) as an important measurement of functional status of an individual, particularly people with disabilities and the elderly. The objective of the study is to assess ADL of the elderly in an urban area of Western Maharashtra.

Methods: This cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted in an urban community in Western Maharashtra. The demographic data was collected after taking informed consent. A total of 300 elderly people who met the inclusion criteria were included in the study. Data was collected as per a pre-tested and validated questionnaire administered by the investigators. It consisted of two parts – personal particulars and Katz Index of Independence to assess ADL. This questionnaire assesses the index of independence in ADL directed towards the activities of bathing, dressing, feeding, transferring and toileting.

Results: About 60.66% of the subjects belonged to the 60–70 years age group. The study cohort was predominantly male (56.33%) while the remaining were females (43.67%). The highest level of dependence among all activities was observed in continence (26.67%) followed by feeding (24.67%), transferring (23%), toileting (22.67%), bathing (22.33) and dressing (20.67%).

Conclusion: The dependency increases with the age. As the aging population expands, so do the challenges in addressing disability and unmet needs among the elderly.

Keywords: Activities of Daily Living (ADL), Katz Index of Independence, Elderly, Urban Area.

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Introduction

Population ageing, characterized by an increasing proportion of elderly individuals in a population, represents a significant global demographic transformation that will intensify as the twenty-first century progresses. This phenomenon arises from the demographic transition, where reductions in mortality are followed by reductions in fertility. This transition leads to a relative reduction in the proportion of children and an increase in the share of people in the main working age and older person groups in the population. [1]

Globally, the number of elderly individuals (aged 60 and above) is projected to exceed the number of children (under the age of 14) for the first time in 2047 and are expected to outnumber children under the age of ten by 2030 (UN World Population Age-

ing, 2013 & 2017) [2]. This demographic trend represents a historic achievement in terms of increased longevity but also offers unpredictable challenges with profound implications on society, health, and the economy.

In Asia and the Pacific, the population ageing process is occurring at an unprecedented pace due to rapid decreases in fertility rates, followed by mortality rates and increases in life expectancy. In 2019, the number of people aged 60 years and older was 1 billion. This number will increase to 1.4 billion by 2030 and 2.1 billion by 2050 [3]. The age group of older persons is getting older too: by 2050, the “oldest-old” (80 years or older) will constitute about one fifth of all older persons. [4] In India, the percentage of the elderly has been in-

creasing swiftly in recent years and is likely to continue in the coming decades. The share of population over the age of 60 years is projected to increase from 10.5 percent in 2022 to 20.8 percent in 2050. By the end of the century, the elderly will constitute over 36 percent of the total population of the country. [5] Also there is a higher percentage of women among the elderly population. The senior sex ratio (females vs. males) is 1065/1000. [6]

This demographic shift has significant implications for society, health, and the economy. Activities of daily living (ADLs) are a crucial aspect of daily life, encompassing self-care within the home, outdoor environments, or both. Health professionals use the ability or inability to perform ADLs as a key indicator of an individual's functional status, particularly for those with disabilities and the elderly. As the population ages, ensuring that older persons can maintain their independence and perform ADLs without assistance will be crucial for their overall well-being and quality of life. [7]

The World Health Organization (WHO) [8] developed a definition of healthy ageing. It is the process of developing and maintaining the functional ability that enables well being in older age. The UN Decade of Healthy Ageing (2021-2030) [9] recognizes the far-reaching impact of population ageing, extending beyond just health systems. It aims to address implications on labor, finance, social protection, and education through collaborative action in four key areas: changing attitudes towards age, developing age-friendly environments, delivering person-centered integrated care, and providing access to quality long-term care. This holistic approach seeks to empower older persons, support their families, and enable societies to harness the benefits of population ageing.

To address the challenges and opportunities presented by population ageing, governments and healthcare systems must develop comprehensive strategies that prioritize lifelong education and healthcare, long-term care, and employment opportunities for older persons.

Additionally, policies should focus on promoting healthy life, social protection, and income security for older individuals, as well as addressing age-based discrimination and exclusion. By doing so, the benefits of population ageing can be maximized, and the challenges can be managed effectively, ensuring a better future for all ages.

Aim and Objectives

Aim of the study is to assess Activities of Daily Living of Elderly aged 60 years and above in an Urban Area of Western Maharashtra and the objective is to determine the functional status of elderly aged 60 years and above living in an urban

area of Western Maharashtra using Katz ADL index.

Materials and methods:

This cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted in an urban community in Western Maharashtra. The data was collected as part of a cross-sectional survey conducted amongst the elderly of this area. The demographic data and profile were studied after taking informed consent. The study population was all elderly people 60 years & above age group living in urban area of Western Maharashtra. The socioeconomic status was calculated using the modified Kuppaswamy scale of socioeconomic status considering the education, occupation and monthly family income [10].

The sample size was calculated by estimating the prevalence of ADL limitation in 60 years & above age group, assuming level of confidence of 95% and absolute error of margin of 5% with the prevalence of ADL limitation in 60 years & above age group as 23.8% [11] according to Longitudinal Ageing Study in India (LASI) Wave 1 study done in year 2017-18. The sample size was computed by using the formula:

$$n = Z^2(1 - \alpha/2) P (1 - P) / d^2$$

The minimum required sample size is 278. Assuming the non-response rate of 10% the final sample size was taken as 300.

A total of 300 elderly people who met the inclusion criteria were included in the study. Data was collected as per a pre-tested and validated questionnaire with sections on informed consent, procedures, the voluntary nature of participation, confidentiality and anonymity declarations, sociodemographic details and Katz Index of Independence in ADL. It was administered by the investigators. The Katz Index of Independence in ADL is the tool to assess the Activities of Daily Living (ADL). This questionnaire assesses the index of independence in ADL being directed towards the activities of bathing, dressing, feeding, transferring and toileting.

The activities that can be done with Independence i.e. no supervision, direction or personal assistance required were given a Point 1 and those done with Dependence i.e. with supervision, direction, personal assistance or total care were given Point 0. So, the scoring ranged from 0 to 6. Bathing Independence was defined as one who bathes self completely or needs help in bathing only a single part of the body such as the back, genital area or disabled extremity and with dependence is defined as need help with bathing more than one part of the body, getting in or out of the tub or shower or requires total bathing. Dressing with independence was defined as one who can get clothes from

closets and drawers and puts on clothes and outer garments complete with fasteners may have help tying shoes and with dependence the one who needs help with dressing self or needs to be completely dressed. Toileting with independence was defined as one who goes to toilet, gets on and off, arranges clothes, cleans genital area without help and with dependence was defined as one who needs help transferring to the toilet, cleaning self or uses bedpan or commode. Transferring with independence was defined as moves in and out of bed or chair unassisted and mechanical transfer aids are acceptable and with dependence is defined as needs help in moving from bed to chair or requires a complete transfer. Continence with independence was defined as exercises complete self-control over urination and defecation and with dependence is defined as partially or totally incontinent of bowel or bladder. Feeding with independence was defined as gets food from plate into mouth without help and preparation of food may be done by another person and feeding with dependence is defined as needs partial or total help with feeding or requires parenteral feeding. These definitions are already validated in the Katz Index of Independence in Activities of Daily Living [12]. The study was carried out for a duration of 4 months (Dec 2023-Mar 2024). Average time taken

for completing one questionnaire was ten minutes. The collected data was recorded in a computerized spreadsheet (Microsoft Excel, Office 365) and analysed using IBM SPSS (Statistics for Windows, Version 26.0. Armonk, NY, USA: IBM Corp)

Inclusion Criteria: A person who has lived at the place of enumeration (this house) for 6 months or more during the last year or intends to live there for at least 6 months in the next year. This may include ‘rotating’ parents, or older people who have lived in the household for more than 6 months during the last year.

Exclusion Criteria: A person who has neither lived at the place of enumeration for 6 months during the last year nor intends to live there for at least 6 months in the future.

Results and Discussion:

Age distribution of the respondents is given in Table 1; 60.66% of respondents were in the age of 60–70 years followed by 26.66% in 71-80 years age group and 10.66% and 2.00% in age group 81-90 years and more than 91 years respectively. The mean age of study participants was 70.16 ± 8.4 years. The sex distribution is given in Figure 1, 43.67% (131) were females and 56.33% (169) were males.

Table 1: Age Distribution

Age Group	N (%)
60-70	182 (60.67)
71-80	080 (26.67)
81-90	032 (10.66)
>91	006 (02.00)
Total	300 (100)

Figure 1: Sex Distribution

The characteristics of elderly by sociodemographic variables are given in Table 2. 88% of elderly belonged to Hindu religion, 73.67% were married and 25% were widow/widower and only 1.33% were divorced. Most of the elderly were graduate 42.33% and 24.33% were educated up to High school. 38.48% belonged to Upper Middle Class followed by 39.66% in Upper Class and 28.77% in Lower Middle Class according to the modified

Kuppuswamy scale of socioeconomic status [10]. Most of the elderly population were retired (70.33%). 45.33% of the population were living with their spouse and 39% were living with family members and only 15.67% of the elderly were living alone. 32% of elderly intake some form of tobacco and 47.33% of elderly reported alcohol intake. 37.33% of elderly were physically active and used to go for a morning or evening walk daily.

Table 2: Characteristics of Elderly by Sociodemographic Variables

Sociodemographic Variables		N (%)
Religion	Hindu	264 (88.00%)
	Muslim	032 (10.67%)
	Sikh	004 (01.33%)
Marital Status	Married	221 (73.67%)
	Divorced	004 (01.33%)
	Widow/Widower	75 (25.00%)
Education	Primary School	26 (08.67%)
	High School	73 (24.33%)
	Diploma	48 (16.00%)
	Graduate	127 (42.33%)
	Postgraduate	026 (08.67%)
Socioeconomic Status	Upper Class	088 (29.33%)
	Upper Middle Class	119(39.67%)
	Lower Middle Class	080 (26.67%)
	Upper Lower Class	013 (04.33%)
Occupation	Business	032 (10.67%)
	Private Job	057 (19.00%)
	Retired	211 (70.33%)
Living Arrangement	Alone	047 (15.67%)
	With spouse	136 (45.33%)
	With family	117 (39.00%)
Use Of Tobacco	Yes	096 (32.00%)
	No	204 (68.00%)
Alcohol Intake	Yes	142 (47.33%)
	No	158 (52.67%)
Physical Activity	Yes	112 (37.33%)
	No	188 (62.67%)

Table 3: Distribution of the study population as per their independence or dependence for bathing

Age Group	Independence (%)	Dependence (%)	Total (%)
60-70	160 (87.91)	022 (12.09)	182 (100.00)
71-80	058 (72.50)	022 (27.50)	080 (100.00)
81-90	015 (46.88)	017 (53.12)	032 (100.00)
>91	000 (00.00)	006 (100.00)	006 (100.00)
Total	233 (77.67)	067 (22.33)	300 (100.00)

Table 4: Distribution of the study population as per their independence or dependence for dressing

Age Group	Independence	Dependence	Total
60-70	158 (86.81)	024 (13.19)	182 (100.00)
71-80	063 (78.75)	017 (21.25)	080 (100.00)
81-90	017 (53.12)	015 (46.88)	032 (100.00)
>91	000 (00.00)	006 (100.00)	006 (100.00)
Total	238 (79.33)	062 (20.67)	300 (100.00)

Table 5: Distribution of the study population as per their independence or dependence for toileting

Age Group	Independence	Dependence	Total
60-70	160 (87.91)	022 (12.09)	182 (100.00)
71-80	060 (75.00)	020 (25.00)	080 (100.00)
81-90	012 (37.50)	020 (62.50)	032 (100.00)
>91	000 (00.00)	006 (100.00)	006 (100.00)
Total	232 (77.33)	068 (22.67)	300 (100.00)

Table 6: Distribution of the study population as per their independence or dependence for transferring

Age Group	Independence	Dependence	Total
60-70	159 (87.36)	023 (12.64)	182 (100.00)
71-80	060 (75.00)	020 (25.00)	080 (100.00)
81-90	012 (37.50)	020 (62.50)	032 (100.00)
>91	000 (00.00)	006 (100.00)	006 (100.00)
Total	231 (77.00)	069 (23.00)	300 (100.00)

Table 7: Distribution of the study population as per their independence or dependence for continence

Age Group	Independence	Dependence	Total
60-70	159 (87.36)	023 (12.64)	182 (100.00)
71-80	054 (67.50)	026 (32.50)	080 (100.00)
81-90	007 (21.87)	025 (78.13)	032 (100.00)
>91	000 (00.00)	006 (100.00)	006 (100.00)
Total	220 (73.33)	080 (26.67)	300 (100.00)

Table 8: Distribution of the study population as per their independence or dependence for feeding

Age Group	Independence	Dependence	Total
60-70	161 (88.46)	021 (11.54)	182 (100.00)
71-80	055 (68.75)	025 (31.25)	080 (100.00)
81-90	010 (31.25)	022 (68.75)	032 (100.00)
>91	000 (00.00)	006 (100.00)	006 (100.00)
Total	226 (75.33)	74 (24.67)	300 (100.00)

The distribution of the study population as per their independence or dependence for the Activities of Daily Living is given in Tables 3 - 8. The figures in parenthesis correspond to the respective percentages. The highest level of dependence among all activities was observed in continence, followed by feeding and then by transferring, toileting, bathing and dressing.

The distribution of the study population as per their independence or dependence for bathing purposes is given in table 3. It was observed that 77.67% of individuals were able to bathe independently, while 22.33% of the study population required assistance from family members or attendants. Additionally, some individuals used assistive devices and railings for support in the bathing areas. The distribution of the study population as per their independence or dependence for dressing up is as shown in table 4.

In the present study, 79.33% of participants were found to dress themselves independently. However, the dependency on assistance increased with the age of the individuals but this was not found to be statistically significant (p value 0.23). Similarly, 77.33% of the study subjects managed their toilet activities independently, with dependence also rising as individuals aged. (Table 5). The

distribution of the study population as per their independence or dependence for transferring is as shown in table 6.

It was observed that approximately 77% of the subjects could move independently from one place to another without requiring assistance from another person. This figure includes individuals who used assistive devices to aid their mobility. Approximately 26.67% of the study population relied on attendants or relatives for basic continence functions, with this dependence increasing with age. (Table 7) In the present study, it was also observed that over 75.33% of individuals could feed themselves independently. (Table 8) However, about 24.67% relied on family members or attendants for feeding. As with other activities, dependence increased with age.

Discussion

The current study findings are largely in sync with the existing evidence that the dependence for the Activities of Daily Living increases with the increasing particularly the Longitudinal Ageing Study in India (LASI) study wave 1 which showed that 23.8% of the people aged 60 years and above had any ADL limitations. [11] Another study which

utilized the LASI, 2017–18 data reported that around 3% of the elderly had severe ADL disability. [13] Another study observed found that activity limitation was significantly more pervasive among the elderly population aged 70 years and above.[14] Das RA et al in their community-based cross-sectional study conducted in Kerala, India, found that functional limitation was significantly more prevalent among the elderly aged above 70 years. [15] Sekhon H et al in their cross-sectional descriptive in 2014 study observed that there was no difference between males and females in ADL. The study also revealed that dependency increased with age in both genders. These findings are similar to those of our current study, [16].Gupta et al in their study conducted in Haryana, observed that prevalence of ADL limitations was less among males as compared to females.[17]. These findings are in contrast to those of our present study.

The present study found that 79.13% of the participants were able to dress themselves independently, with dependency increasing with age. [18] This is in sync with another study carried out by Sonn U which observed that 83% of individuals at age 70 were independent in all activities.

Regarding specific ADL ,the highest level of dependence among all activities was observed in continence which is similar to the findings of another study carried out by Sekhon H et al [16] However, the present study found that only 78.05% had the ability of self-bathing, which is also similar to another study which reported ability of self-bathing as 79%. [16] Both the current study and the LASI Wave 1 study found that around 8% of the people aged 60 years and above used a walker or walking stick.[11] indicating consistency in this particular finding. These findings are also corroborated by another study which showed that maximum number of elderly was using walking stick and spectacles. [14]

In our study findings the most common problems encountered by elderly were joint pain, visual impairment, backache and gastritis. These findings are in sync with previous studies carried out by Das RA et al and Peter RM et al [15] [19] These findings of our present study, also align with the notion that as individuals progress into the later stages of older adulthood, they are more likely to experience age-related health conditions and functional impairments. The consistent evidence across studies underscores the need for targeted interventions and comprehensive healthcare approaches to address the unique challenges faced by the elderly population, particularly those in the advanced stages of aging.

Conclusion & Recommendation

Disability is a crucial indicator of quality of life, as it captures both diseased and non-diseased individuals, providing a more comprehensive assessment of well-being compared to traditional morbidity and mortality data. The Katz Index of Independence in Activities of Daily Living is a useful tool to assess the Activities of Daily Living and can be used further for more studies. Ensuring good quality geriatric health care services at the primary level and basing them on the "felt needs" of the elderly population is essential. Promoting physical activity through community-based programs tailored to their needs can positively impact their well-being.

At the tertiary care level, geriatric wards and specialized training for healthcare providers in geriatric care are necessary. Capacity building for different health personnel, including "Community Geriatric Health Workers" to provide home care, is crucial. In conclusion, addressing population ageing in India requires a multifaceted approach that prioritizes the needs of the elderly, improves access to geriatric care, promotes physical activity, and fosters a supportive social environment. This can ensure a better quality of life for the rapidly growing elderly population.

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